

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SQUEEZE CAST ZINC-ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The primary drawback in the utilization of zinc-aluminum (Zn-Al) alloys for industrial applications is the poor elevated temperature ($>100^{\circ}\text{C}$) mechanical properties of the alloys. A viable approach of improving the elevated temperature properties is to reinforce the Zn-Al alloys with ceramic fibers to form Zn-Al composites. In this study, the preform fabrication aspects of squeeze casting Zn-Al composites are addressed. It is found that the amount of binder material that is used to prepare the ceramic preforms has a significant effect on the tensile properties and fracture toughness of the resulting composites. The influence of the binder material on the mechanical properties is explained from the fracture mechanism standpoint and using results obtained with transmission electron microscopy on the fiber/matrix interfaces.

Key Words : Composite materials; Zinc base alloys; Alumina fibers; Squeeze casting; Mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to their excellent castability and good mechanical properties, zinc-aluminum (Zn-Al) alloys are being utilized in many industrial applications (1,2). However, despite attractive room temperature properties, Zn-Al alloys have unsatisfactory elevated temperature properties. Degradation of the tensile strength and creep resistance occurs at temperatures above approximately 100°C . Because of this limitation, the extent of applications of the alloys has been restricted to those for low service temperature.

An attractive possibility of improving the elevated temperature properties of Zn-Al alloys up to 150°C is by fiber reinforcement to form a metal matrix composite. The potential advantages which can be gained include improvement of the strength, modulus of elasticity, creep and wear resistance (3-9). Previous work has shown that the loss of strength of the unreinforced Zn-32Al alloy is caused by the softening of the zinc-rich interdendritic phases at 150°C , resulting in an interdendritic mode of failure at this temperature (3,4). By reinforcing the Zn-32Al matrix with about 20 vol% Al_2O_3 fibers, the interdendritic failure could be avoided, resulting in higher tensile properties at 150°C . However, the mode of failure of the 20 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-32Al}$ composite was dominated by fiber/matrix interface failure. Auger Electron Spectroscopy analysis of fracture surfaces revealed the presence of binder material on the surface of the decohered fibers as well as

in the matching depressions in the Zn-Al matrix. These observations showed that the SiO₂ binder used to fabricate the Al₂O₃ preform provides an easy path for crack propagation, resulting in lower ductility and toughness than expected (5).

In this work, the effects of Al₂O₃ preform preparation conditions on the mechanical properties of squeeze cast Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al composites are discussed. The tensile and fracture toughness properties of 18 vol% Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al prepared using different amounts of SiO₂ binder are evaluated and the results of detailed SEM and TEM examination of the fracture surfaces and fiber/matrix interfaces are reported.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

All squeeze cast materials evaluated in this work were fabricated at MTL/CANMET. The chemical composition (wt%) of the Zn-Al alloy used to fabricate the composites is given as follows:

Al	Cu	Fe	Mg	Si	Zn
27.0	2.06	0.065	0.012	0.012	balance

The following materials were squeeze cast in the form of discs having the dimensions 80 mm diameter and 40 mm thickness : (i) Zn-27Al, (ii) 17.2 vol% Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced Zn-27Al prepared using 0.2 vol% SiO₂ binder and (iii) 18.8 vol% Al₂O₃ fiber reinforced Zn-27Al prepared using 4.0 vol% SiO₂ binder. The difference in volume fraction of Al₂O₃ fibers between the two composites is not considered significant from the point of view of the mechanical properties. The Saffil Al₂O₃ fibers were produced by ICI and are reported to consist of 96-97% delta alumina and 3-4% silica. The length of the as-received fibers is 1-2 mm and their median diameter is 3 μm.

Squeeze casting of the Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al composites took place in two stages. The first stage was the fabrication of a preform by mixing the fibers with a silica binder to hold them in a three-dimensional network. With the mixing technique used for the present work, the fibers were aligned randomly in the transverse plane of the preform. The second stage was the pressure infiltration of the preform by the molten Zn-27Al alloy. The preform was placed in a die and preheated to approximately 400°C. The die cavity was filled with Zn-27Al alloy superheated to about 80°C above its melting temperature and a punch was gradually lowered into the die, forcing the molten alloy to infiltrate the preform. The pressure exerted by the punch on the molten metal was gradually increased to a pre-determined level of 95 MPa (9). The applied pressure was maintained at this level for about 1.5 min., until the molten metal was completely solidified. On completion of the squeeze casting operation, the punch was retracted from the die and the composite product was removed by an ejector fitted in the bottom of the die.

For tensile testing, sub-sized specimens complying with ASTM E-8, with a 25.4 mm gage length and 6.35 mm gage diameter, were machined from the squeeze cast Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al discs. The specimens were soaked at 150±1°C for 20 min. and tested on an Instron model 8562 tensile testing machine using a strain rate of 3.33x10⁻⁴ sec⁻¹ and an extensometer for recording the strain.

The plane-strain, chevron-notch fracture toughness of the Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al composites was determined using short bar specimens complying with ASTM E-1304. The dimensions of the short bar specimens were 12.7 mm thickness, 19.685 mm length and 11.049 mm height. A chevron notch with a thickness of 0.260 mm was cut with a diamond blade. The specimens were soaked at 150±1°C for 10 min. Six valid replicate tests were performed for each material.

To evaluate the microstructure of the composite materials, sectioned and polished tensile specimens were examined in the Scanning Electron Microscope using Back Scattered Electron

(BSE) imaging to provide atomic number contrast. For Transmission Electron Microscopy, thin slices were cut from the region immediately below the fracture surface of broken tensile specimens using a low speed diamond saw. The slices were mechanically polished to about 100 μm thickness and dimpled mechanically with diamond paste in a Gatan Dimpler Grinder. The dimpled specimens were ion milled to perforation in an Ion Tech Thinning apparatus. Thin foils were examined in a Philips EM400T TEM/STEM operated at 120kV and fitted with an Edax 9100 EDS system for X-ray detection.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Microstructure

The microstructure of the two $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites was composed of a random planar array of Al_2O_3 fibers surrounded by the Zn-27Al matrix (Figures 1a and 1b). The fibers were uniformly distributed in the specimen with 0.2% SiO_2 binder despite the lower amount of binder used to hold the fibers together during the squeeze casting operation (Figure 1b).

The Zn-27Al matrix of the composites was composed of small (10 to 50 μm) rounded primary aluminum-rich phases surrounded by fine lamellar $\alpha+\eta$ eutectoid and zinc-rich interdendritic phases (Figures 1c and 1d). The Al_2O_3 fibers were associated with the latter, which is the last phase to solidify in the Zn-27Al alloy. This indicates that during the squeeze casting operation, solidification begins in the areas between the fibers. Large patches of SiO_2 binder, appearing as a black phase in the BSE micrographs, were observed at the fiber contact points and on the surface of some fibers in the specimen having a high binder content (Figure 1c). Only small amounts of binder were detected in the specimen which had a low binder content (Figure 1d).

The fiber/matrix interface microstructure of the two composites was also examined with TEM. In the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ containing 4% binder, patches of SiO_2 inter-connecting the fibers were observed (Figure 2) as well as a layer of SiO_2 covering many of the fibers. The SiO_2 binder was identified by its amorphous structure and its Si content, as determined by EDX analysis. The matrix material could be distinguished by its crystalline nature and the presence of strong peaks of either Al or Zn, with occasional low peaks of Cu. In thick regions of the foil, cracks were observed in the binder phase between adjacent fibers, confirming that the interface was a favored crack propagation path. Hardly any binder could be detected in the specimen with a low binder content (0.2% SiO_2) and no cracks were observed at the fiber/matrix interfaces.

3.2. Mechanical Properties

Table 1 lists the mechanical property results obtained for the squeeze cast Zn-27Al and the two $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites. Both composites show an improvement in yield strength and ultimate tensile strength over the unreinforced squeeze cast Zn-27Al. The results also show that a reduction from 4% to 0.2% in the amount of binder used to fabricate the preform resulted in a 31% increase of the ultimate tensile strength and a 260% increase of the tensile elongation measured at 150°C. The yield strength is only increased by 12% and the modulus of elasticity does not appear to be significantly influenced by the reduction in binder content. It is apparent that the amount of binder present in the composite has only a small influence on the load-bearing capacity of the composite. However, the amount of binder has a significant effect on the ductility and fracture toughness of the squeeze cast $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$. Reducing the binder content from 4% to 0.2% increased the fracture toughness measured at 150°C by 22% (Table 1). Figure 3 shows representative load-displacement curves obtained during the fracture toughness testing of the composites. The crack extension was smooth, with no evidence of crack jump behavior.

The fracture surfaces of selected short bar fracture toughness specimens were examined in the SEM. The fracture surface of the composite prepared using 4% binder was composed of numerous decohered fibers surrounded by finely dimpled Zn-Al matrix (Figure 4a). In many areas, patches of fragmented binder could be observed at fiber contact points. The fiber/matrix

interface obviously provided an easy path for crack propagation in this material, resulting in low fracture toughness. The fractographic features of the composite prepared using 0.2% binder were significantly different (Figure 4b). The Al₂O₃ fibers were well bonded to the matrix and were observed at the bottom of shallow depressions in the Zn-Al matrix. The fracture surface was dominated by extensive tearing of the Zn-Al matrix, indicating that a ductile mode of failure was prevalent and explaining the higher value of fracture toughness measured for this material.

Table 1. Mechanical Properties of Squeeze Cast Zn-27Al and Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al Composites at 150°C.

Material	Yield Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	Elongation in 25.4 mm (%)	Modulus (GPa)	K _{I_{VM}} (MPa·m ^{1/2})
Unreinforced Zn-27Al	101±6	156±3	7 - 13	10.9 (at 25°C)*	-
18.8 vol% Al ₂ O ₃ Reinforced Zn-27Al 4% SiO ₂ binder	154±12	201±7	0.57±0.04	70.4±12.5	8.9±0.7
17.2 vol% Al ₂ O ₃ Reinforced Zn-27Al 0.2% SiO ₂ binder	173±17	264±20	2.07±0.21	67.7±5.6	10.9±0.6

*ref. 10

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Reinforcement of Zn-27Al with 18 vol% Al₂O₃ fibers provides improved tensile properties at 150°C. The yield strength is increased by 50 to 70% and the ultimate tensile strength is increased by 30 to 70% depending upon the amount of binder used in the Al₂O₃ fiber preform fabrication.
2. The presence of an excessive amount of silica binder at the fiber/matrix interfaces results in extensive fiber/matrix decohesion under tensile and plane strain crack propagation loading, severely reducing the ultimate tensile strength, ductility and fracture toughness of Al₂O₃/Zn-27Al composites.
3. A reduction in the amount of binder used to fabricate the Al₂O₃ preform from 4% to 0.2% is sufficient to produce a 31% increase in ultimate tensile strength, 260% increase in tensile elongation and 22% increase in fracture toughness measured at 150°C. The preform fabricated using 0.2% binder retained sufficient strength to be easily handled without damage during the squeeze casting operation.

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(a) 18.8 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite with 4% SiO_2 binder.

(b) 17.2 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite with 0.2% SiO_2 binder.

(c) Higher magnification of 4% SiO_2 binder specimen showing large patches of binder at the fiber contact points (arrows).

(d) Higher magnification of 0.2% SiO_2 binder specimen. Only small amounts of binder are visible at the fiber contact points (arrows).

Figure 1. BSE Micrographs of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites.

Figure 2. TEM micrograph of 18.8 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite with 4% SiO_2 binder.

Figure 3. Load-displacement curves obtained during fracture toughness testing of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composites.

(a) 18.8 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite with 4% SiO_2 binder.

(b) 17.2 vol% $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Zn-27Al}$ composite with 0.2% SiO_2 binder.

Figure 4. SEM fractographs of fracture toughness specimens.